

SPARC: Enhancing Engineering Learning Through AI and Gamification

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Abstract

Rapid advances in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and gamification have paved the way for transformative advances in engineering education, enabling innovative solutions to improve student engagement and learning. This paper explores the integration of AI-driven systems within educational frameworks, focusing on the game SPARC (Systematic Problem Solving and Algorithmic Reasoning for Children). SPARC exemplifies the potential of combining AI technologies, such as peer agents, with customized, serious games to create a student-centered learning environment aligned with science and engineering curricula standards.

Through immersive storytelling, decision-making scenarios, and adaptive challenges, SPARC fosters critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaborative learning in K-12 and engineering education. The interactive environment encourages active exploration, where players refine their understanding through trial-and-error mechanics, peer discussions, and scaffolded feedback loops, reinforcing both individual and cooperative learning experiences. The latest version of SPARC integrates AI-driven peer agents that act as interactive learning companions, guiding students through the gameplay. Unlike traditional AI tutors, SPARC's peer agents engage students in structured dialogues, prompting them to articulate reasoning and refine conceptual understanding.

Pilot studies and user feedback indicate SPARC's effectiveness in increasing engagement and understanding of complex engineering concepts. More than 80% of the participants reported increased interest in STEM subjects after playing the game, proving its value as a scalable and innovative educational tool.

This paper explores the technical and design challenges of optimizing AI-driven educational systems, offering strategies to enhance their effectiveness. Furthermore, it discusses opportunities to extend SPARC's application to broader engineering education contexts. By integrating advanced AI capabilities and gamified learning strategies, SPARC demonstrates the potential of

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AI-driven education to enhance student learning experiences. This research provides insights for future innovations in AI-enhanced engineering education.

Introduction

Overview of AI and gamification in modern education

Education is transforming with the popularity of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the changing gaming audience. The aim is to improve student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. AI-powered education systems use machine learning models, intelligent tutoring, and adaptive feedback mechanisms to personalize instruction and meet the needs of diverse learners. Meanwhile, gamification introduces game elements such as storytelling, challenges, rewards, and interactive simulations to create engaging learning experiences. Research has shown that a well-designed and balanced educational game is well suited to increase student motivation, problem-solving skills, and knowledge retention since the early beginnings of gamified learning in the 1980s³.

Although, in general, gamified education is not currently widespread, research on motivation to play suggests that a balance between intrinsic (e.g., curiosity, challenge, self-improvement) and extrinsic motivation (e.g., rewards, competition, achievement tracking) promotes long-term engagement in learning⁵. Self-Determination Theory (SDT) suggests that games can enhance autonomy, competence, and social relationships to make learning more effective¹. Building on this again, the development of AI systems is the perfect complement to these game mechanics, dynamically adapting content based on learner performance to ensure that educational challenges are kept at optimal difficulty.

Importance of engineering education in the AI era

As AI and large language models (LLM) redefine industries, engineering education must adapt so that students not only need to understand AI, but also need to be able to think computationally, solve problems, and reason algorithmically. The traditional lecture-based teaching model involves the instructor as the giver and the student is often left to be the passive recipient. The drawback of this model is that students cannot actively participate or develop the ability to solve real-world problems, which leads to low knowledge transfer and application skills². In contrast, AI-powered educational games provide contextualized learning experiences where students can apply engineering principles in simulated environments, reinforcing conceptual understanding and technical proficiency¹⁰. In addition, engineering education faces accessibility challenges, especially in underrepresented communities. Artificial intelligence-powered games can bridge this gap by providing low-cost, scalable, and adaptive learning solutions that ensure equitable access to education⁹.

Introduction to SPARC and its educational goals

SPARC (Systematic Problem-Solving and Algorithmic Reasoning for Children) is an AI-powered serious game designed to improve the engineering and computational thinking skills of K-12

students. It integrates narrative-driven learning, intelligent peer agents, and adaptive game mechanics to create an interactive and engaging educational experience.

SPARC's key educational goals include:

- Enhance students' understanding of the life science of human blood circulation and the physics of motion and force through interactive exploration.
- Develop problem-solving skills and computational thinking by immersing students in event-based reasoning tasks.
- Encourage collaboration and knowledge transfer through multiplayer game mechanics and organized peer interactions.
- Enhance student motivation by providing an engaging and meaningful learning environment that prepares students for STEM careers.

Unlike traditional AI tutors, SPARC's AI-powered peer agents function as learning partners rather than instructors, fostering trust through companionship and play, and guiding students through structured conversations that encourage critical thinking and self-reflection. By embedding game-based learning principles such as challenge-based progression, immediate feedback, and free exploration, SPARC improves self-directed learning and collaborative problem-solving. Pilot studies show that more than 80% of students report increased interest in STEM subjects after playing SPARC, demonstrating SPARC's potential as a scalable and innovative educational tool. As an evolving platform, SPARC will continue to be improved through iterative user testing, teacher feedback, and AI-driven optimizations to increase engagement and learning.

SPARC: A Case Study in Innovation

Development and Implementation of SPARC

SPARC (Systematic Problem Solving and Algorithmic Reasoning for Children) is a narrative-driven, multiplayer mobile game that immerses students in a contextualized scientific conceptual, yet engaging, journey through a simulation of the human blood circulation. SPARC was developed to improve K-12 students' computational thinking, problem-solving skills, and STEM engagement.

Integrating game mechanics with learning

SPARC is designed to align game mechanics with curriculum-based learning objectives. Its goal is to provide an interactive, context-rich environment where students engage with scientific concepts through exploration and problem-solving. The games include three core educational strategies:

- Narrative-driven learning contexts:
Inspired by the "Magic School Bus", SPARC allows students to shrink and explore the human body in a rocket, interacting with cells and organs. The game connects abstract scientific concepts with real-world applications to help students visualize molecular structures, circulatory pathways, and physiological processes. For example, an introduction

to human cells begins with a video on animal cell formation as shown in Fig.1(a), which prepares students for an in-depth exploration of blood cells, oxygen transport, and blood-oxygen exchange.

- Collaboration and self-directed learning opportunities:
SPARC balances multiplayer collaboration with individual exploration, reflecting the dual nature of real-world learning environments. For collaboration parts, players are organized in groups of up to four and can view both team scores and individual rankings as shown in Fig.1(b). Team communication channels as shown in Fig.1(c) promote real-time collaboration, problem-solving, and engagement. While for independent Challenges, each game module allows students to navigate the environment, interact with anthropomorphic characters, and solve puzzles at their own pace. For example, in the Meeting Cells module, players have to search for white blood cells in a maze-like network of blood vessels, while keeping an eye out for traces of viruses as clues.
- Balance between free exploration and guidance
To accommodate different learning styles, SPARC includes both open-ended exploration and structured instruction. The game's storyline provides subtle hints through character dialog (e.g., red blood cells provide clues on how to find white blood cells as shown in Fig.1(d)). Knowledge maps are embedded in the game to help students visually connect key concepts and reinforce learning.

(a) Start exploration into an animal cell.

(b) Player ranking board.

(c) player team chat.

(d) Red leads to find White.

Figure 1: Multiple game designs.

Iterative development and refinement

The development of SPARC follows an iterative process that synthesizes teacher and student feedback to refine gameplay, align with curriculum standards, and improve usability.

- Improvements in content and games:
One example is the “Meeting Cells” module. It was originally designed as a “runner’s game” in which students navigate obstacles to recognize red blood cells, white blood cells, platelets, and albumin as shown in Fig.2(a). In the new version, players now navigate a realistic network of blood vessels instead of the usual obstacles while learning about oxygen transport and immune responses as shown in Fig.2(c). Another example is The “Thumping Heart” module. It initially required students to jump on a mat to match their heart rate as shown in Fig.2(b). However, after observing students’ difficulties with jumping skills, the module was converted into a rhythm-based musical game in which players synchronize beats to simulate changes in heart rate due to temperature, fatigue, or physical activity as shown in Fig.2(d).
- User Interface (UI) and Accessibility Improvements:
 - The initial circular navigation menu was modified to include directional arrows to improve ease of use for students unfamiliar with the game’s controls.

We also introduced further customization options:

 - Players can switch between first-person view and third-person view.
 - We added a left-handed user interface layout to improve ease of use.
 - Players can now choose cartoon-style avatars, reducing distractions from realism.
- Seamless transitions to enhance spatial awareness:
Two-dimensional scenes can now transition between environments (e.g., from blood vessels to the heart), helping students maintain a sense of orientation and an understanding of the body’s interconnected systems.

(a) Old Meeting Cell.

(b) Old Thumping Heart.

(c) New Meeting Cell.

(d) New Thumping Heart.

Figure 2: Game iterations.

Peer Agent and Its Role in Learning Support

In SPARC, the peer agent is designed to function as an interactive non-player character (NPC) that dynamically engages with the player throughout the game. Unlike traditional AI tutors⁸, the peer agent integrates into the narrative, building a relationship with the player and progressively transitioning into a learning companion. This approach fosters both engagement and deeper conceptual understanding.

Role of Peer Agent in Game Interaction

Initially, the peer agent appears as an in-game NPC that interacts with the player, allowing for natural and immersive engagement. Through repeated interactions, the peer agent develops a relationship with the player, transitioning from a background character to an active participant in the storyline. At critical points in the game, the peer agent provides guidance, hints, and prompts to help the player navigate complex problem-solving tasks.

Enhancing Learning Through Peer Teaching

Instead of simply providing direct answers, the peer agent encourages real-time discussions with the player. When an NPC presents a scientific question or concept, the peer agent will express curiosity or doubt, prompting the player to explain the concept in detail as shown in Fig.3. This process transforms the learning experience into an interactive teaching moment, reinforcing knowledge retention by requiring the player to articulate explanations and deepen their understanding.

Figure 3: Cap leads player's talk.

- By engaging in structured dialogues with the player, the peer agent facilitates a learning-by-teaching approach.
- The player must clarify concepts to the peer agent, effectively reinforcing their own understanding while building a sense of responsibility for knowledge transfer.

- Studies on peer learning indicate that teaching others enhances cognitive processing, leading to improved knowledge retention and engagement.
- The integration of real-time discussions ensures that concepts are explored in-depth rather than passively absorbed.

Impact on Engagement and Learning Outcomes

- Early testing indicates that players interacting with the peer agent demonstrate higher engagement and problem-solving persistence.
- Teachers and students report that the peer agent's presence makes the game more immersive and educationally meaningful.
- The design bridges the gap between entertainment and structured learning, reinforcing STEM concepts in an organic and engaging manner.

By embedding the peer agent within SPARC's narrative, the game leverages interactive peer discussions to strengthen learning, increase engagement, and encourage knowledge transfer through an intuitive and immersive approach.

Impact on student engagement, critical thinking, and collaboration

The SPARC program has demonstrated significant educational benefits, particularly in terms of increased student engagement, improved problem-solving skills, and enhanced STEM motivation. The game has been evaluated in several ways, including extensive pilot studies, classroom observations, and teacher feedback, to assess its effectiveness in achieving learning goals.

Increased knowledge of scientific and computational thinking

To measure the effectiveness of SPARC in reinforcing scientific and computational concepts, the research team conducted pre-test and post-test assessments in the areas of circulatory systems, physical principles, and computational problem-solving.

- **Pre- and Post-Test Content Knowledge Growth**
The pre- and post-game tests assessed student learning outcomes in different modules (e.g., Blood circulatory systems, Physics, Computational thinking). From the results we can see, that while there was some increase in student knowledge, the differences were not statistically significant, which may have been due to the small sample size (30 out of 56 complete responses) and implementation challenges (e.g., shared equipment, inconsistent module access). In this case, enhancing the data collection process and ensuring consistency of student access will provide more accurate measures of learning outcomes in future iterations.
- **Real-World Application of STEM Concepts**
Students' ability to apply science and engineering concepts in real-world situations has increased. For example, in the Oxygen Transportation module, students experienced factors such as blood vessel size and blood flow rate and gained an intuitive understanding of physical principles such as friction and motion.

Engagement and motivation in STEM learning

One of the main goals of SPARC is to increase student interest and motivation in STEM. We conduct self-evaluation surveys during our pilot research. And from students' feedback:

- 72% of students believe that SPARC will help their peers understand science concepts.
- 89% of students felt that SPARC was as effective as or better than the traditional curriculum.
- 60.7% saying that SPARC was more effective.
- More than 80% of students indicated that they would like to learn more about human anatomy and science after participating in SPARC.

In addition, from the qualitative Feedback:

- "The game kept me engaged so I was able to get more out of it. I also saw real-life examples of what I learned."
- "The game kept me engrossed and helped me stay focused on what I was learning".
- "I will continue to play the game because it is fun to see what happens next and it is fascinating to explore different parts of the body".

These results show that SPARC effectively captures students' interest and encourages them to further explore STEM topics, which is essential for long-term learning retention and career motivation.

Teacher Engagement and Professional Development

The success of SPARC depends heavily on teacher engagement and integration of classroom instruction. During the project, teachers moved from passive observers to active contributors to the development of SPARC.

- Teacher workshops and feedback integration
Organized workshops and trained teachers in SPARC game mechanics, curriculum adaptation, and curriculum integration. Teachers' feedback directly influenced game improvements, such as:
 - Adding more physics applications to the racing module.
 - Revising pre-test assessments to be more aligned with the curriculum.
 - Enhancing the aesthetics of the game and the accessibility of the user interface.
- Challenges of Classroom Implementation Infrastructure constraints (e.g., school Wi-Fi limitations, and limited device access) impacted seamless integration. Teacher requests for additional resources include:
 - Alternative gaming platforms for non-mobile users.
 - More flexible lesson plans to align SPARC modules with existing curricula.

Enhancing SPARC and Expanding Its Impact on Engineering Education

Addressing the challenges identified in SPARC's development requires a combination of technical improvements, pedagogical strategies, and infrastructure enhancements. In addition, the impact of the game can extend beyond K-12 education to broader applications in engineering and

interdisciplinary STEM learning. This section discusses approaches to improve SPARC's scalability, optimize AI-driven learning, and explore opportunities for further development.

Optimizing AI Performance and Resource Allocation

- Implement lightweight AI models to reduce computational load while maintaining adaptive learning capabilities⁶.
- Transition from cloud-based AI processing to local edge computing⁷ to improve real-time response.
- Continue to use reinforcement learning techniques⁴ to refine AI-generated prompts and interactions based on student behavior dynamically.

Enhancing AI-Driven Personalized Learning

- Implement Dynamic Difficulty Adjustment (DDA) to modify in-game challenges based on player performance.
- Enhance AI-driven peer agents to generate player profiles, which in turn provide context-aware cues and prompts based on individual learning needs.
- Integrate databases to record student performance for tracking, helping educators monitor learning progress and identify areas for intervention.

Conclusion

The SPARC project represents a significant advancement in AI-driven educational gaming, demonstrating the potential of gamified learning environments to enhance STEM education. Through narrative-driven gameplay, AI-powered peer agents, and adaptive learning pathways, SPARC fosters critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaborative engagement among students.

Summary of Findings

- SPARC successfully increased student engagement and motivation in STEM subjects, with over 80% of students reporting greater interest in scientific concepts after gameplay.
- The integration of AI-driven peer agents and adaptive game mechanics enhanced personalized learning experiences, allowing students to interact dynamically with content.
- Pilot studies revealed areas for improvement, including scalability, infrastructure limitations, and the need for refined difficulty adjustment mechanisms to balance engagement and educational rigor.
- Teachers played a crucial role in integrating SPARC into classroom environments, emphasizing the importance of professional development and instructional support for maximizing its effectiveness.

Future Directions

Future plans for SPARC include adding more advanced engineering and STEM topics, especially those related to real-world problems. The AI will be improved to give more helpful and personalized support. Long-term studies will look at how the game affects learning, problem-solving, and career preparation. New technologies like augmented and virtual reality will also be used to make learning more fun and engaging.

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